

1 **Supplementary Information:**
2 **Racing amidst change: urbanization and climate alter functional traits and distribution of**
3 **an Amazonian parthenogenetic lizard**

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15 **1. Materials and Methods**

16 **1.1. Study area & specimens sampling**

17 The survey was realized under SISBIO licenses n. 83159-1/2022 and n° 44832-4. The
18 physiological experiments were realized under CEUA/INPA license n. 042/2020 SEI
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20 The Amazon Forest is often seen as an ocean of trees with wide rivers crossing it,
21 however, it is much heterogeneous, composed by different phytophysiognomies, such as open
22 areas (“Campinas”, Savannas), “Campinaranas”, “Terra Firme” and “Igapó” (flooded area)
23 (Braga, 1979; Adeney et al., 2016; de Carvalho & Mustin, 2017). The campinas and

24 campinaranas are regions with isolated small bushes and arboreal species, respectively (Adeney
25 et al., 2016; Guimarães & Bueno, 2016). Their soil presents mostly sand content with a small
26 clay component, and has low drainage capacity, becoming seasonally flooded in some localities
27 (Adeney et al., 2016; Guimarães & Bueno, 2016). In northern Amazonia, the savannas of
28 Roraima are an enclave of open grasslands (“campo limpo”, “campo sujo”) with a mosaic of
29 shrubs, scattered trees, and forest patches (Barbosa & Miranda, 2004). Thus, we collected
30 individuals and ecological and physiological data in two localities in Brazil with contrasting
31 environments (see Figure S1): Manaus – Amazonas, (hereafter referred to as the neonative
32 population; see Essl et al., 2019), on 03-27, August 2022, and 16-18 January 2023 during the
33 rainy and dry season; and Bonfim – Roraima (hereafter referred to as native population), on 17-
34 22 July 2022, during the rainy season. The precipitation differs between dry and rainy seasons,
35 with accumulated precipitation of 56.1 mm to 347 mm respectively (INMET, 2022). These
36 regions differ in temperature and precipitation. Manaus has a mean of 27.3°C (minimums of
37 23.7°C and maximum of 34.1°C) and annual precipitation of 2,300 mm. In contrast, Roraima’s
38 savannas have a mean of 27.8°C (maximum of 34.3°C and minimums of 22.4°C) and annual
39 precipitation of 1,600 mm (Braga, 1979; Barbosa & Miranda 2004; Corrêa et al., 2016; INMET,
40 2022). However, the urban region of Manaus unveiled an increase in temperature of 0.7°C from
41 1961 to 2008 (Souza & Alvalá, 2014) and might be even hotter nowadays. The soil of Manaus
42 and savannas of Roraima are mainly composed of clay, with some addition of sand and silt
43 (Chauvel et al., 1987; IBGE, 2025).

44 The morphological identification of individuals was made in the field following Recoder
45 et al. (2018) and confirmed with molecular analysis using mtDNA 16S (see below). Lizards were
46 caught through active surveys during the hottest hours of the day (1000 h to 1400 h) in open

47 areas in Bonfim, and next to buildings or/and garden areas in Manaus (Cole et al., 1989; Vitt &
48 Zani, 1998), as these lizards were observed active in the hottest hours of the day even on hot
49 surfaces (Cole et al., 1990). To enhance the sampling effort in Manaus, since '[...] on a good day
50 of collecting, four field workers might catch a total of eight or ten of these lizards [...]' (Cole et
51 al., 1989), we used five miniaturized pitfall traps with about four 1-liter buckets between a fence
52 of 4 m × 30 cm (Figure 1).

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56 Figure 1. Pitfall traps used to collect individuals of *Gymnophthalmus underwoodi* Grant 1958, in
57 Manaus-AM, Brazil. Photos and drawings by the first author.

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1.2. Genetic data

To confirm the identification of sampled individuals with greater accuracy, we extracted genetic samples of the mitochondrial marker 16S (\pm 550 bp) from tissues of the tail muscle and liver of eight collected specimens from Amazonas and Roraima (Table 1). The DNA was extracted following Promega Wizard® Genomic DNA purification Kit. The 16S was amplified following Pellegrino et al., (2001) using primers 16SF (5'-CTGTTTACCAAAAACATMRCCTYTAGC-3') and 16SR (5'-TAGATAGAAACCGACCTGGATT-3'). The purification followed PEG 8000 protocol (Sambrook & Russel, 2001) and was submitted to sequencing following BigDye Terminator 3.0 Cycle Sequencing kit (Applied Biosystems). Additionally, we used all sequences of the species *Gymnophthalmus underwoodi* available in Genbank for phylogenetic analysis, and sequences of *Micrablepharus atticolus* Rodrigues 1996, *M. maximiliani* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862) and *Calyptommatus sinebrachiatus* Rodrigues 1991, as outgroups (Table 1) aligning with Geneious v7.0. To infer the phylogenetic tree, we used MrBayes v.3.2 (Ronquist et al., 2012) through the CIPRES webserver (<http://www.phylo.org/>). The GTR+G was chosen as the best substitution model for the alignment, obtained using MrModelTest v2.4 (Nylander et al., 2008). The Bayesian Inference (BI) was made through two independent runs of 50 million generations each, four Markov chains, and trees sampling every 5,000 generations (Recoder et al., 2018). The *burn-in* of 10% was applied using Tracer v1.7.2 and the final tree was fitted with FigTree v1.4.4.

81 Table 1. Molecular sampling and sequences retrieved from Genbank. Specimens used in this study are in process of deposit in Genbank.

Voucher	Species	Locality	Country	16S	Reference
AMNH-R-138374	<i>Gymnophthalmus cryptus</i>	San Juan de Manapiare, Amazonas	Venezuela	AF101362	Kirizian & Cole, 1999
MTR 946613	<i>Gymnophthalmus leucomystax</i>	Alto Alegre, Roraima	Brazil	AF420715	Pellegrino et al., 2001
AMNH-R-139856	<i>Gymnophthalmus leucomystax</i>	Rupununi Savanna	Guyana	AF101363	Kirizian & Cole, 1999
AMNH-R-139857	<i>Gymnophthalmus leucomystax</i>	Rupununi Savanna	Guyana	MH732714	Recoder et al., 2018
MTR 946618	<i>Gymnophthalmus leucomystax</i>	Alto Alegre, Roraima	Brazil	MH732715	Recoder et al., 2018
AMNH-R-128428	<i>Gymnophthalmus pleii</i>	Martinique	West Indies	AF101364	Kirizian & Cole, 1999
MTR 33465	<i>Gymnophthalmus speciosus</i>	San José	Costa Rica	MH732710	Recoder et al., 2018
ALM 5979	<i>Gymnophthalmus</i> cf. <i>speciosus</i>	Adicora, Falcón	Venezuela	AF101367	Kirizian & Cole, 1999
JC/FT7054	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	St. Phillip	Barbados	AF101369	Kirizian & Cole, 1999
APL 21703	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Manaus, Amazonas	Brazil	MH732712	Recoder et al., 2018
INPA-H044762	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Manaus, Amazonas	Brazil	OR438308	This study
INPA-H044761	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Manaus, Amazonas	Brazil	OR438309	This study
INPA-H044753	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Manaus, Amazonas	Brazil	OR438310	This study
INPA-H044769	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Manaus, Amazonas	Brazil	OR438311	This study
INPA-H044759	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Manaus, Amazonas	Brazil	OR438312	This study
INPA-H044760	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Manaus, Amazonas	Brazil	OR438313	This study
INPA-H044764	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Manaus, Amazonas	Brazil	OR438314	This study

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INPA-H044752	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Manaus, Amazonas	Brazil	OR438315	This study
INPA-H044745	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	São João da Baliza, Roraima	Brazil	OR438316	This study
INPA-H044744	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	São João da Baliza, Roraima	Brazil	OR438317	This study
INPA-H044730	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Bonfim, Roraima	Brazil	OR438318	This study
INPA-H044728	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Bonfim, Roraima	Brazil	OR438319	This study
INPA-H044726	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Bonfim, Roraima	Brazil	OR438320	This study
INPA-H044732	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Bonfim, Roraima	Brazil	OR438321	This study
INPA-H044729	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Bonfim, Roraima	Brazil	OR438322	This study
INPA-H044740	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Bonfim, Roraima	Brazil	OR438323	This study
INPA-H044734	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Bonfim, Roraima	Brazil	OR438324	This study
INPA-H044735	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Bonfim, Roraima	Brazil	OR438325	This study
MTR 946590	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Ilha de Maracá, Roraima	Brazil	KT254406	Goicoechea et al., 2016
NYSM 6432	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Bottomless Ghaut	Montserrat	KX866265	Snyder et al., 2017
MPEG 33517	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Belém, Pará	Brazil	MZ544022	Maciel et al., 2021
MTR 946601	<i>Gymnophthalmus underwoodi</i>	Ilha de Maracá, Roraima	Brazil	MH732711	Recoder et al., 2018
MTR 946639	<i>Gymnophthalmus vanzoi</i>	Alto Alegre, Roraima	Brazil	AF420743	Pellegrino et al., 2001
MTR 946484	<i>Gymnophthalmus vanzoi</i>	Boa Vista, Roraima	Brazil	MH732699	Recoder et al., 2018
MTR 946500	<i>Gymnophthalmus vanzoi</i>	Normandia, Roraima	Brazil	MH732705	Recoder et al., 2018
MTR 946529	<i>Gymnophthalmus vanzoi</i>	Uiramutã, Roraima	Brazil	MH732708	Recoder et al., 2018

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MPEG 29841	<i>Gymnophthalmus vanzoi</i>	Mazagão, Amapá	Brazil	MZ544020	Maciel et al., 2021
MTR 33447	<i>Gymnophthalmus vanzoi</i>	Santarém, Pará	Brazil	MH732695	Recoder et al., 2018
AMNH-R-140975	<i>Gymnophthalmus</i> aff. <i>vanzoi</i>	Berbice River	Guyana	AF101366	Kirizian & Cole 1999
AMNH-R-128438	<i>Gymnophthalmus</i> aff. <i>vanzoi</i>	St. George	Trinidad and Tobago	MH732709	Recoder et al., 2018
LG 854	<i>Micrablepharus atticolus</i> *	Santa Rita do Araguaia, Goiás	Brazil	AF420718	Pellegrino et al., 2001
LG 1017	<i>Micrablepharus maximiliani</i> *	Barra do Garças, Mato Grosso	Brazil	AF420730	Pellegrino et al., 2001
MRT 05054	<i>Calyptommatus sinebrachiatus</i> *	Gentio do Ouro, Bahia	Brazil	AF420720	Pellegrino et al., 2001

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* species set as outgroup in phylogenetic analysis

83 1.3. Preferential and voluntary temperatures

84 The collected specimens were kept individually isolated in plastic recipients with
85 moistened paper and without access to food. These conditions were maintained for
86 approximately four days in an isolated room with air temperature ranging from 26 to 30°C. The
87 abstention from food was made to avoid the effects of diet on preferred temperature (T_{pref})
88 (Gilbert & Miles, 2016; Simandle et al., 2001; Abayarathna & Webb, 2021). The thermal tests
89 were conducted sequentially, starting with the assessment of preferred temperature (T_{pref}),
90 followed by sprint performance, and concluding with the determination of critical temperatures.
91 Each individual passed through all experiments.

92 We determined the T_{pref} using a thermal gradient made of plastic roof lining measuring
93 1,00 m × 1,00 m × 0,33 m, split into eight channels with a width of 12.50 cm each (Paranjpe et
94 al., 2012) (Fig. 2). We used a zinc plate as the base of the gradient, with ice bags at one end and
95 60W incandescent light bulbs covered with yellow cellophane paper at the other end to reduce
96 the effects of color during the thermoregulation (Fleishman et al., 2011; Pérez I de Lanuza et al.,
97 2018). The thermal gradient ranged from 40°C to 10°C in each channel. The temperature range
98 used in this experiment aligns with those commonly applied in similar studies (e.g., Camacho et
99 al., 2014; Diele-Viegas et al., 2018; Martins et al., 2021) and closely matches the thermal
100 conditions experienced by the species in its natural habitat. In Manaus, air temperatures range
101 from a minimum of 23.7°C to a maximum of 34.1°C, while in Boa Vista, they range from
102 22.4°C to 24.3°C. Additionally, Cole et al. (1990) observed that *G. underwoodi* individuals
103 select areas with maximum air temperatures around 40.0°C. The individuals were acclimated for
104 30 minutes inside the thermal gradient before starting the measurements. We placed the lizards
105 in the middle of the lane to reduce the chance of directional bias. Using a small thermocouple

106 (Omega[®] 5SC-TT-T-36-72 *Ready-Made Insulated Thermocouple with Kapton[®], PFA, Glass*
107 *Braid Insulation and Molded Connector*) attached to the lizards' belly with hospital tape, we
108 recorded the lizards' body temperature every minute for 120 minutes on the gradient with a data-
109 logger (Omega[®] TC-08-TC-DAQ *8-Channel USB Thermocouple Data Acquisition Module*). To
110 minimize stress, as the core-surface temperature does not change significantly in small animals,
111 the thermocouple was attached to the lizards' belly with hospital tape (Camacho et al., 2014;
112 Diele-Viegas et al., 2018). The T_{pref} was determined as the mean of the body temperatures
113 recorded during the experiment, with the 5th percentile representing the voluntary minimum
114 temperature (VT_{min}), and the 95th percentile representing the voluntary maximum temperature
115 (VT_{max}) (Caetano et al., 2020).

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119 Figure 2. Structure to perform the Preferential Temperature test (T_{pref}). Support with 60W
120 incandescent light bulbs covered with yellow cellophane paper (a); Zinc plate with sandpaper to
121 facilitate the mobility of individuals (b); Ice bags (c). Drawings by the first author.

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124 **1.4. Sprint performance**

125 After inferring the T_{pref} , we measured the sprint performance. We built a linear track with plastic

126 roof lining measuring 1.00 m × 0.30 m × 0.30 m (Fig. 3). To measure the performance across

127 different substrates, the base of the track was made with two types of substrates (herein

128 treatments): one with red clay to represent native environment (native substrate); and the other

129 with coarse-grain sandpaper (60 grit; grains ~400 μm) to simulate the street substrate in the

130 urban environment (urban substrate). We selected these substrates since *G. underwoodi* is a

131 lizard commonly found in gardens and near houses in urban environments, frequently observed

132 active during the hottest hours of the day on warm surfaces. They are usually encountered

133 running through the grass in gardens, but individuals can also be found on human-made surfaces

134 such as concrete, walls, and streets. The first author recorded one individual near a street at the

135 Universidade Federal do Amazonas (UFAM), published on iNaturalist

136 (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/129431075>), while another observation was made

137 between university buildings where students attend classes

138 (<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/136613349>). Another collection site was an apartment

139 complex (-03.091350, -59.989627), where individuals had no way to enter or leave the area

140 without crossing streets and other cemented surfaces. Additionally, we filmed an individual

141 climbing a cement wall in an urban environment, which can be viewed at the link

142 <https://youtu.be/i4X32hPchQ0>.

143 Other researchers have also documented individuals on human-made structures, such as

144 streets (which we used as one of our substrates). Maciel et al. (2021) found individuals in fluvial

145 port areas, while Alfonso et al. (2012) observed individuals basking in leaf litter between
146 buildings on the University of Oriente campus. In their natural Amazonian habitat, these lizards
147 inhabit leaf litter or grass in open vegetation, open forests, and sandy riverbanks (Ávila-Pires
148 1995; Ribeiro-Júnior & Amaral 2017). However, in the savanna region where some specimens
149 were collected, the terrain consists mainly of open areas with predominantly clay-rich soil
150 (<https://www.ibge.gov.br/geociencias/informacoes-ambientais/pedologia/15829-solos.html>;
151 Adeney et al. 2016).

152 Therefore, we chose to use coarse-grain sandpaper as a substrate because urban
153 individuals frequently traverse human-made surfaces, particularly streets and cemented areas. At
154 the same time, we selected clay as a substrate due to its prevalence in the savanna region and the
155 limitations of using grass in experimental tests. While artificial grass could have been an option,
156 the grass structure in their natural habitat is not uniform. Additionally, due to the small size of
157 these lizards (40 mm SVL), they are difficult to spot in leaf litter and grass, as noted by Cole et
158 al. (1989): '*Spotting the small, shiny brown lizards is a bigger problem.*'

159 To record the sprint during the 1.0 m, we used a digital camera (Casio Exilim Ex-FH20
160 9.1MP) attached to a tripod about 1.30 m over the track, and we shot at 400 frames for a second.
161 Individuals from each study area were randomly divided into two groups (n = 9 each), with each
162 group assigned to one of the substrate treatments. We decided not to use the same individual for
163 both substrates to keep the data independent and avoid repeating measurements for the same
164 lizard. Additionally, minimizing the handling of individuals helped reduce stress and prevented
165 fatigue, which could negatively affect their performance. By allowing each individual to run on
166 only one substrate and limiting the number of trials per individual, we ensured that their
167 performance remained consistent and unaffected by exhaustion during the experiment. The

168 experiment was conducted with one lizard at a time, and each lizard ran two times in rapid
169 succession at three different temperatures with a two-hour recovery period between runs. The
170 first run was conducted with body temperature at room temperature (26 – 30°C), the second at -
171 5°C relative to the initial temperature, and the third at +5°C relative to the initial temperature.
172 The selection of temperature conditions followed an adaptation of the methodology described by
173 Diele-Viegas et al. (2018) and the recommendations provided by Taylor et al. (2020). While both
174 studies applied or suggested five or more temperature classes, only three temperature conditions
175 were used in this study. However, strict temperature classes were not predefined, as individual
176 lizards exhibited natural temperature variation. Consequently, the experiment effectively tested
177 more than five temperature points. These variations were essential for constructing the thermal
178 performance curve (TPC). The decision to increase body temperature last was based on the
179 suggestion that higher temperatures pose a greater risk to individuals compared to lower
180 temperatures (Taylor et al., 2020). We classified each of the two runs as either 'good' or 'bad'
181 for further analysis. The 'good' run was defined as the one in which the lizard crossed the track
182 with few stops, while the 'bad' run was characterized by the lizard returning to the starting point
183 or stopping several times. Only the 'good' runs were used for analysis. To reach the required
184 temperature, we placed the lizards inside a styrofoam box with an ice bag and with 60W
185 incandescent light bulbs to decrease and increase the body temperature (Fig. 4). The body
186 temperature was measured through the cloaca using an ultrafine thermocouple connected to an
187 automatic thermometer (Omega[®] HH806AU accuracy 0.3°C). We did not use the surface
188 temperature here to avoid measuring our own temperature, since we needed to hold the specimen
189 for about 30 seconds to be able to measure. The sprint speed was calculated as the mean of

190 'good' run of each temperature (three different temperatures per lizard) and disregarding
191 moments that they stopped, using Tracker v5.1.5 (available at www.physlets.org/tracker).
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195 Figure 3. Structure to perform the Sprint performance. Bottom lane treatment with clay (native
196 treatment); Upper lane treatment with sandpaper 60 grit grains $\sim 400 \mu\text{m}$ (neonative treatment).
197 The track was split in distances of 0.25 m. Drawings by the first author.

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201 Figure 4. Structure to increase and reduce the body temperature of the individuals. Box with
202 icebags to reduce the body temperature (a); Box with 60w incandescent light bulb to increase the
203 body temperature (b). Drawings by the first author.

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206 1.5. Critical minimum and maximum

207 Two hours after the final sprint performance test, we proceeded to measure the critical
208 minimum (CT_{\min}) and critical maximum (CT_{\max}) temperatures, with CT_{\max} being the final trait
209 assessed for each lizard. To reach these critical temperatures, we used the same equipment as for
210 sprint performance (described above). CT_{\min} was measured when the lizard lost its righting
211 response, while CT_{\max} was measured when the lizard exhibited spasms and lost its righting
212 response (Taylor et al., 2020). To reduce the effect of holding the individual, we placed them on
213 a plastic recipient. Between tests, the lizards had a four-hour rest period to recover. Immediately
214 after the temperature measurement, we restore the lizard's body temperature to normal levels

215 using a 60W incandescent light bulb for CT_{min} and a water bath for CT_{max} . The rate of change in
216 temperature was not measured. All individuals were euthanized with xylazine 2%, fixed with
217 10% formalin, and deposited at the Amphibians and Reptiles Collection from the Instituto
218 Nacional de Pesquisas da Amazônia (INPA-H) at the end of the tests.

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220 **1.6. Morphological measurements**

221 To assess the effect of urbanization on morphology and its effect on sprint performance,
222 we measured the morphological traits of individuals. Both specimens collected by our study and
223 specimens previously deposited at the INPA-H Collection (n = 14) were measured. However,
224 only those specimens collected by our study were used to assess the effect of morphology on
225 sprint performance. The specimens were photographed in lateral, dorsal and ventral view, with a
226 digital camera Nikon D3400 with a lens DX 18-55 mm 1:3.5-5.6 G equipped with a generic
227 *close-up* filter (+2) (Figure 5), to measure the traits using ImageJ v1.54b (Schneider et al., 2012;
228 precision of 0.0001 mm). We measured 16 traits (Figure 6) including snout-vent length (SVL);
229 head width (HW); head height (HH); head length (HL); trunk length (TRL); interbrachial-nasal
230 length (INL); femur length (FL); tibia length (TL); hindfoot length (FTL); humeral length (HL);
231 forearm length (FAL); tail length (TAL); pelvic girdle (PG); shoulder girdle (SG); and counted
232 scales of the third finger of hindfoot (SHF), and third finger of forefoot (SFF) (Recoder et al.,
233 2013; Winchell et al., 2018; Vaughn et al., 2021). Furthermore, we measured both the left (_L)
234 and right (_R) sides of each limb to assess fluctuating asymmetry (FA) (Palmer & Strobeck,
235 1986; Lazić et al., 2013), while for the other analyses we used only the left side. The traits were
236 measured twice on different days and in a different order, and remeasured those that differed by
237 more than 10%. We used just adults in morphological analyses, and we defined them as having

238 SVL > 35 mm (Hardy et al., 1989) and the development of sexual gonads. The use of ImageJ for
239 measuring animals, particularly lizards, has been validated by Lambert et al. (2012), who
240 demonstrated that its accuracy is comparable to caliper measurements, with a difference of only
241 one standard deviation. Additionally, our measurements differ by 0.7% to 24.3% (Table 2) from
242 those reported by Recoder et al. (2018), who used calipers to measure the same lizard species.
243 While the percentage differences may seem substantial, the absolute values remain closely
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248 Figure 5. Standardized photographs used for lizard measurements. These images illustrate the
249 photographic methodology used for morphometric and meristic analyses. (a) Ventral view of the

250 entire body; (b) Lateral view of the entire body; (c) Ventral view with a close-up of the hindfoot
251 for lamellae counting; (d) Ventral view with a close-up of the forefoot for lamellae counting.

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255 Figure 6. Morphological traits measured. HW: head width; HH: head height; HL: head length;
256 TRL: trunk length; INL: interbrachial-nasal length; HUL: humeral length; FAL: forearm length;
257 FL: femur length; TL: tibia length; FTL: hind foot length; SVL: Snout-vent length; TAL: tail
258 length; PG: pelvic girdle; SG: shoulder girdle; SHF: scales of the third finger of hindfoot; SFF:
259 scales of the third finger of forefoot. Drawings by the first author.

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261 Table 2. A comparison made between the measurements taken by Recoder et al. (2018) using a
 262 caliper and those obtained by us using ImageJ v1.54b. HW: head width; HH: head height; HL:
 263 head length; TRL: trunk length; INL: interbrachial-nasal length; HUL: humeral length; FAL:
 264 forearm length; FL: femur length; TL: tibia length; FTL: hind foot length; SVL: Snout–vent
 265 length; TAL: tail length.

Trait	Recoder et al. 2018 (n=16)	This work (both population, juveniles and adults; n = 75)	Difference between average values in %
SVL	36.2 (26.6-41.7) mm	38.7 (25.2-48.6) mm	6.8
TRL	20.9 (15.4-25.3) mm	20.7 (12.6-27.0) mm	1.0
HH	2.9 (2.3-3.6) mm	3.5 (2.6-4.3) mm	21.3
HW	4.5 (3.9-5.0) mm	5.3 (3.7-6.4) mm	17.8
HL	6.6 (5.3-7.3) mm	6.5 (5.1-7.7) mm	1.2
FEM/FL	4.4 (2.7-5.1) mm	4.4 (3.0-5.2) mm	0.7
TIB/TL	3.8 (2.5-4.3) mm	3.1 (1.9-3.9) mm	19.1
FTL	6.2 (5.0-6.7) mm	6.4 (4.4-7.4) mm	3.5
HUM/HUL	2.7 (1.9-3.1) mm	3.1 (2.1-4.1) mm	15.6
FAL	6.3 (4.7-7.3) mm	6.2 (4.5-7.1) mm	1.8
TAL	61.6 (n = 5; 52.5- 69.6) mm	46.7 (n = 65; 10.5- 75.6) mm	24.3

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267 1.7. Data analysis

268 All analyses were performed using R software v4.2.1 (R Core Team 2022). The scripts
 269 and raw data can be accessed on Dryad (see Main Text). Individuals who died during the tests
 270 were not used for thermal analyses, only for morphology.

271 CT_{\min} , CT_{\max} , and T_{pref} were compared between the neonative and native populations
272 using function *t-tests*, following Silva et al. (2022) (Table 3). To compare sprint performance
273 between populations, we constructed a thermal performance curve (TPC) using a generalized
274 additive mixed model (GAMM) implemented in the *mgcv* v1.8 package (Wood, 2001). The TPC
275 was generated by setting the velocities at the values of CT_{\min} and CT_{\max} to zero (Taylor et al.,
276 2020). Morphological traits that exhibited differences between the native and neonative
277 populations were included in the TPC analysis, along with the treatment and geographic
278 distribution, all treated as fixed factors. The curve's smoothness was determined by population
279 as group parameters, and individuals were considered as random factors. Model selection was
280 performed using *MuMin* v1.47.1 package (Bartoń, 2022). We selected the model with an AICc
281 difference smaller than 2 ($\Delta < 2$), from the model with the lowest AICc. Graphs were made using
282 the *ggplot2* package (Wickham, 2011). The temperature at which the lizard reached the highest
283 performance was assumed as the thermal optimum performance (T_{opt}), and the thermal
284 performance breadth was calculated as the range of temperatures where at least 80% of the
285 maximum performance is achieved (B80) (Taylor et al., 2020).

286 Before comparing the morphology of the neonative and native populations, we assessed
287 the dependence of morphological traits on snout-vent length using a linear model (*lm*). When the
288 relationship was statistically significant, the residuals of the *lm* were used for further analysis.
289 We compared the SVL between neonative and native populations using a t-test. To visualize the
290 morphological differences, we performed a principal component analysis (PCA) using *prcomp*
291 function with the data *z-score* standardized. The results of PCA can be seen in Table S1 and
292 Figure S2. The morphological differences between populations (neonative \times native) were
293 assessed using a non-parametric multivariate analysis of variance (NP-MANOVA) with residual

294 randomization in permutation procedure (RRPP; Collyer & Adams, 2018) employing 99999
295 permutations, following Telemeco and Gangloff (2020). This approach generates empirical
296 sampling distributions by randomly permuting the residuals, reducing the chances of Type-I
297 error and the concern regarding the number of variables and sample size (Telemeco & Gangloff,
298 2020). The values of the least-square mean result from RRPP can be seen in Table 4.

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317 Table 3. Results of *t.test* of thermal traits between neonative and native populations. The
 318 normality of data was assessed using Shapiro-Wilk and LeveneTest. T_{pref}: preferential
 319 temperature; CT_{max}: critical maximum temperature; CT_{min}: critical minimum temperature.

Trait	Population	N	Mean	sd	se	<i>t_test</i>		
						t	df	p-value
T _{pref}	Neonative	18	32.7078	1.8213	0.4293	0.8658	33	0.3928
	Native	17	32.2435	1.29866	0.3150			
CT _{max}	Neonative	18	45.0500	0.8459	0.1994	0.8055	34	0.4261
	Native	18	44.8556	0.5772	0.1361			
CT _{min}	Neonative	18	15.5889	1.2024	0.2834	-4.3398	34	0.0001
	Native	18	17.6500	1.6169	0.3811			

Trait	Population	Shapiro-Wilk		LeveneTest		
		W	p-value	df	F value	Pr(>F)
T _{pref}	Neonative	0.97413	0.5661	1	0.3635	0.5507
	Native			33		
CT _{max}	Neonative	0.9461	0.0788	1	0.5071	0.4812
	Native			34		
CT _{min}	Neonative	0.95848	0.1929	1	2.0987	0.1566
	Native			34		

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321 Table 4. Least-square of predicted values from NP-MANOVA with residual randomization in
 322 permutation procedure. All traits were used as residual values of the linear regression between
 323 the trait and SVL in PCA. HW: head width; HH: head height; HL: head length; TRL: trunk
 324 length; INL: interbrachial-nasal length; HUL: humeral length; FAL: forearm length; FL: femur
 325 length; TL: tibia length; FTL: hindfoot length; TAL: tail length; PG: pelvic girdle; SG: shoulder
 326 girdle; SHF: scales of the third finger of hindfoot; SFF: scales of the third finger of forefoot.

Trait	Neonative			Native		
	Mean	95% lower confidence	95% upper confidence	Mean	95% lower confidence	95% upper confidence
HL	-0.0186	-0.3750	0.3614	0.0241	-0.3904	0.4743
HH	0.3590	0.0295	0.6917	-0.5032	-0.8936	-0.1097
HW	-0.0750	-0.4407	0.2865	0.1056	-0.3262	0.5349
TRL	0.3886	0.0731	0.7226	-0.5448	-0.9164	-0.1514
INL	-0.4722	-0.7813	-0.1739	0.6616	0.3007	1.0174
SG	-0.1052	-0.4685	0.2607	0.1503	-0.2755	0.5824
PG	0.1100	-0.2419	0.4793	-0.1528	-0.5683	0.2882
FL	-0.2448	-0.5887	0.1085	0.3415	-0.0669	0.7629
TL	0.1897	-0.1635	0.5538	-0.2657	-0.6802	0.1581
FTL	0.5835	0.3189	0.8456	-0.8155	-1.1272	-0.5057
HUL	-0.0569	-0.4430	0.2925	0.0814	-0.3729	0.4895
FAL	0.4449	0.1314	0.7511	-0.6216	-0.9924	-0.2622
SHF	0.3364	-0.0014	0.6586	-0.4706	-0.8736	-0.0768
SFF	0.1112	-0.2530	0.4739	-0.1526	-0.5860	0.2784
TAL	-0.0468	-0.4194	0.3184	0.0647	-0.3685	0.4937

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329 To assess the fluctuating asymmetry (FA), we followed Lazić et al., (2013). First, we
 330 calculated an asymmetry index (AI) for all traits as the value on the right side minus on the left
 331 side ($AI_{trait1} = R_{side} - L_{side}$) (see mean values in Table S4), where positive values suggest
 332 right dominance and negative values suggest left dominance. Second, we assessed trait size
 333 dependence on total body size using a linear regression between asymmetry index and SVL (AI
 334 $\sim SVL$) (Table 5) and the dependence on own trait size using a linear regression between
 335 asymmetry index and the average between left and right measures of each trait [$AI \sim (R + L)/2$]
 336 (Table 6). Third, we assessed whether distributions have directional asymmetry (DA) or FA
 337 through a linear mixed-effect model (LMM) with the package *nlme* (Pinheiro et al., 2023). The
 338 LMM was performed with the original data for each population for each morphological trait
 339 separately. Morphological traits were set as fixed factors between side and their interaction with
 340 specimens (side:specimen), both as fixed factors, and specimen measurements as random factors.
 341 For the count of scales of hindfoot and forefoot (SHF and SFF) we used the family poisson in
 342 *glmmTMB* package (Brooks et al., 2017). Finally, we compared the FA between the native and
 343 neonative populations using a one-way ANOVA. For the comparison, we calculate the absolute
 344 AI values with averages of each morphological trait value corrected using the log10
 345 transformation ($AI_{trait1} = |\log(\bar{x} R_{side}) - \log(\bar{x} L_{side})|$)

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348 Table 5. Results of analysis of variance (ANOVA) assessing the relation of asymmetry index
 349 (AI) of morphology measures with snout-vent length (SVL). HUL: humeral length; FAL:
 350 forearm length; FL: femur length; TL: tibia length; FTL: hindfoot length; SFT: scales of the third
 351 finger of hindfoot; SHF: scales of the third finger of forefoot; Sd: standard deviation; Se:

352 standard error; Df: degrees of freedom.

Trait	Df	Sum sq	Mean sq	F value	Pr(>F)
FL	1	0.1862	0.1862	2.3018	0.1323
TL	1	0.0077	0.0077	0.1510	0.6984
FTL	1	0.2090	0.2090	2.2864	0.1336
HUL	1	0.0234	0.0234	0.5389	0.4646
FAL	1	0.0997	0.0997	1.3193	0.2534
SHF	1	0.1950	0.1947	0.5318	0.4675
SFF	1	0.1500	0.1500	0.3687	0.5450

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355 Table 6. Results of analysis of variance (ANOVA) assessing the relation of asymmetry index

356 (AI) of morphology measures with trait size $(Right_{side} + Left_{side})/2$. HUL: humeral length;

357 FAL: forearm length; FL: femur length; TL: tibia length; FTL: hind foot length; SFT: scales of

358 the third finger of hindfoot; SHF: scales of the third finger of forefoot; Sd: standard deviation;

359 Se: standard error; Df: degrees of freedom.

Trait	Df	Sum sq	mean sq	F value	Pr(>F)
FL	1	0.2241	0.2241	2.7839	0.0983
TL	1	0.1140	0.1140	2.2850	0.1337
FTL	1	0.2155	0.2155	2.3594	0.1276
HUL	1	0.1609	0.1609	3.8294	0.0531
FAL	1	0.2085	0.2085	2.7984	0.0974
SHF	1	0.0340	0.0345	0.0937	0.7601
SFF	1	0.0410	0.0411	0.1007	0.7516

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362 **1.8. Inferring species distribution and extinction risks**

363 To assess the current distribution of *Gymnophthalmus underwoodi*, infer its potential
364 dispersion routes and its local extinction risks, we performed a hybrid species distribution model.
365 We chose the hybrid model since this approach has been shown as a more complete method to
366 assess the effects of climate change on species (Meineri et al., 2015; Caetano et al., 2020;
367 Tourinho & Vale, 2023).

368 We selected four types of predictors: (1) Bioclimatic variables, available at WorldClim
369 (<https://www.worldclim.org/>) (Fick & Hijmans 2017); (2) Soil content (percentage of clay, silt,
370 and sand) available in Soilgrid (<https://soilgrids.org/>) (Hengl et al., 2017) for 0.0 and 5 cm
371 depths; (3) Landcover based on Global land-use and land cover change (LUCC) (available at
372 <https://geosimulation.cn/GlobalLUCCProduct.html>) (Li et al., 2017); (4) Slope acquired through
373 altitude using function *terrain*; and (5) Ecophysiological variables, the hour of activity (H_a) and
374 sprint performance. We excluded four bioclimatic variables that showed spatial anomalies in the
375 study area (Bio07, Bio16, Bio18, and Bio19). For the remaining 15 variables left, we used
376 variance inflation factor (VIF) with a threshold of 10 to reduce multicollinearity while changing
377 Bio02 (Mean Diurnal Range) for Bio05 (Maximum Temperature of Warmest Month), and Bio12
378 (Annual Precipitation) for Bio15 (Precipitation Seasonality) since extreme are important to
379 assess species vulnerability (Román-Palacios & Wiens, 2020). The landcover was used as a
380 continuous raster, where all forest biomes were set as 1 and grassland as 0. We used two
381 scenarios of forest predictions in the future models, where the pessimistic scenario A2 was used
382 for SSP5-8.5 and moderate scenario A1B for SSP3-7.0 (Sales et al., 2020). The ecophysiological
383 variables were derived from the functional data we collected and geographically projected using
384 the microclim method in the Mapinguari package (<https://gabrielhoc.github.io/Mapinguari.html>;

385 Caetano et al., 2020) and the microclim database of Kearney et al. (2014). We used the TPC
386 calculated before (see Data Analysis) since this is a proxy to Darwinian fitness usually used for
387 lizards (Angilletta 2009; Taylor et al., 2020), and hours of activity (H_a), an important predictor
388 for assessing the effects of climate change (Caetano et al., 2020; Sinervo et al., 2010). All
389 variables were aggregated to 2.5' (~ 5 km) spatial resolution. The correlation among all
390 predictors was assessed using VIF (>10), resulting in the final 11 variables selected (Dormann et
391 al., 2013; James et al., 2021; Sillero et al., 2021). We predicted the species distribution under two
392 climate change scenarios: moderate (SSP3-7.0) and extreme (SSP5-8.5), for the years 2060 and
393 2100 (Riahi et al., 2017; IPCC 2021). To account for uncertainty, we choose four different global
394 climate models (IPSL-CM6A-LR, MIROC6, MRI-ESM2-0, and UKESM10LL) that represent a
395 good projection in the study area (Cannon, 2020).

396 We delimited the accessible area with a minimum convex polygon with a 500 km buffer
397 (Barve et al., 2011; Mendes et al., 2020; Sillero et al., 2021). This area almost covers the entire
398 distribution of the genus *Gymnophthalmus*, thus covering a large variability of climate conditions
399 available (Elith et al., 2010; Escobar et al., 2014; Sillero et al., 2021). However, we extrapolate
400 the model to an area that ranges from latitude -90° to -45° , and longitude -10° to 25° to evaluate
401 possible future areas of dispersion. The distribution records used were obtained through our own
402 field records, literature records, GBIF (available at <https://www.gbif.org/>), and iNaturalist
403 (available at <https://www.inaturalist.org/>), using only unique occurrences (157 total) (available
404 on Dryad). We used an environmental filter, *EnvSample* function, that reduces environmental
405 bias using the grid resolution of the variables (Varela et al., 2014), only with predictors selected
406 with $VIF < 2$ (seven in total) from those 11 sets above, leaving 103 records. Additionally, we used
407 a 10 km buffer (Castellanos et al., 2019) to reduce geographic biases, keeping 75 records.

408 We performed the SDM with package *ENMTML* (Andrade et al., 2020) using four
409 algorithms: Maximum Entropy (presence and background) (Phillips et al., 2006), Bayesian
410 Gaussian Process (presence and pseudo-absence) (Golding, 2014; Golding & Purse, 2016),
411 Random Forest (presence and pseudo-absence) (Liaw & Wiener, 2002), and Support Vector
412 Machine (presence and pseudo-absence) (Karatzoglou et al., 2004). The final model was
413 generated by the ensemble of models by the weighted mean of Sørensen index (Leroy et al.,
414 2018), maximizing the true positives to evaluate the models. This increases the capacity of
415 discriminating between presence and absence sites, avoiding bias by the prevalence of data (ratio
416 between species occupancy area and study area) (Leroy et al., 2018). The choice of the four
417 algorithms was based on their general performance in default settings and in the type of data
418 necessary for their execution (absence and background), allowing a better ensemble (Sillero et
419 al., 2021; Valavi et al., 2022; 2023). In addition, we performed the model using the Bioclim and
420 generalized linear models algorithms (also available in *ENMTML*), however, they did not
421 perform well (low values of AUC, TSS, and Sørensen), so we excluded them from the analysis.
422 The number of pseudo-absences represents fake locations where the species is not observed,
423 being equal to presences (ratio equal to 1) (Andrade et al., 2020). These pseudo-absences were
424 allocated outside a 50 km buffer, following the default parameters of the package (Barbet-Massin
425 et al., 2012). The background points are the locations for climate sampling of the environment,
426 and the number was determined following the default parameter (10,000) (Andrade et al., 2020).
427 The data partition was made using the 'checkerboard' cross-validation approach to reduce the
428 spatial correlation (Roberts et al., 2017). Sørensen and TSS metrics (Allouche et al., 2006; Leroy
429 et al., 2018), were used for model evaluation in which values close to +1 suggest a good model.

430 The model ensemble resulted in a threshold of 0.32 (Table 7) that was used to make a
 431 binary plot and estimate the area of occurrence. The estimated area of occurrence was calculated
 432 using the same polygon from the accessible area. The current and future binary plots were
 433 overlapped to assess which areas are considered stable, and in which areas *Gymnophthalmus*
 434 *underwoodi* is forecast to lose or gain ranges.

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437 Table 7. Evaluation table of Species Distribution Model for *Gymnophthalmus underwoodi*. The
 438 ensemble model was made using the weighted mean of the Sørensen index. Threshold was
 439 calculated using the Sørensen index. AUC was not used to select the best model however we
 440 chose to inform since it is a common evaluation metric. MXD: Maximum Entropy default (all
 441 features); SVM: Support Vector Machine; RDF: Random Forest; GAU: Bayesian Gaussian
 442 Process.

Algorithm	Threshold	AUC	TSS	Sørensen
MXD	0.99	0.82	0.60	0.78
SVM	0.71	0.86	0.66	0.84
RDF	0.59	0.83	0.58	0.80
GAU	0.60	0.84	0.62	0.81
Ensemble	0.32	0.86	0.70	0.84

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